

ECO-EFFICIENCY EVALUATION ON THE RECYCLING OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER

Xiang Li¹, Ruibin Bai¹, Jon Mckechnie²

¹Department of Science and Engineering, University of Nottingham
Taikang Road No.199, Ningbo, China
Email: xiang.li@nottingham.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.nottingham.edu.cn>

²Division of Energy and Sustainability, University of Nottingham
University Park, Nottingham, UK

Keywords: eco-efficiency evaluation, life cycle assessment, waste of carbon fibre
ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) is widely used in aerospace applications, and will increasingly be used in automotive applications into the future. A large quantity of composites waste is therefore generated from manufacturing processes and end-of-life vehicles. Recovering value from CFRP waste can help to address the high cost and environmental burden of producing carbon fibres.

Life cycle costing and environmental assessment methods are applied in this study to quantify the financial and environmental impacts of alternative waste CFRP treatment routes. Thus, we formed a set of combined indicators including total cost and global warming potential (GWP). Three CFRP waste treatment routes are evaluated: landfilling; incineration with energy recovery; and mechanical recycling. Fibre recovered by mechanical recycling output is evaluated as a substitute for glass fibre and carbon fibre, depending on fibre properties and application.

In the absence of regulation, landfill represents the least-cost CFRP waste treatment of those considered. When Landfill Tax legislation is included in the analysis, incineration is preferred from a cost perspective. However, relative to landfill, incineration is associated with increased greenhouse gas emissions: carbon released from CFRP during combustion exceeds CO₂ emissions savings from displacing UK electricity and/or heat generation. The financial and environmental performance of mechanical recycling for recycling of CFRP is heavily dependent on the materials they can displace. On-going development of carbon fibre recovery technologies and composite manufacturing techniques using recycled carbon fibres will lead to improved material properties and is therefore critical to ensuring financial viability and environmental benefit of CFRP recycling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforcement polymer (CFRP) has already been used as a popular light weight material in aviation applications and nowadays is increasingly used in automotive applications. In view of the environmental impacts, fuel saving can be achieved when CFRP is used in place of heavier materials such as steel. However, difficulties in recycling CFRP waste results in an environmental burden at its end-of-life, whereas steel is more easily recovered and current recycling rates normally exceed 75% [1].

To address the difficulties of CFRP recycling, a number of methods have been successfully trialled including mechanical recycling, pyrolysis and fluidised bed processes [2]. However, uncertain economic viability of recycling process and the markets for recycled material are two key factors influencing the implementation of CFRP recycling. As a result, CFRP may enter conventional waste treatment routes (landfill, incineration). This paper aims at studying the financial and environmental (energy use, global warming potential) impacts of possible CFRP waste treatments: landfill, mechanical recycling and incineration by combined heat incinerator.

2 METHODS

The goal of this study is to assess the environmental impact and financial performance of alternative waste CFRP treatments. Life cycle inventory (LCI) models are developed to quantify energy use and global warming potential (GWP) associated with waste CFRP treatments. Life cycle cost (LCC) models are developed to calculate the total cost of waste treatment, including collection, separation/dismantling, shredding, and treatment processes as well as transportation. We consider three possible end-of-life treatments of waste CFRP materials: landfilling, incineration with energy recovery; and mechanical recycling to recover materials for use as fibre reinforcement and/or filler material.

2.1 Life cycle inventory

Life cycle environmental evaluations are performed based on matrix-based computation LCI method which has been described in [3]. “Gate to grave” modules are developed for CFRP waste treatment by landfilling and incineration, beginning at the point where end-of-life vehicle have been collected and including waste processing (disassembly, shredding), transport, and waste treatment (landfill, incineration). For recycling, a “gate to gate” approach is taken to include the production of composite materials from recycled carbon fibres (rCF) and powder recyclate materials in addition to the activities considered for landfilling and incineration routes. Production stage and use stage of CFRP are considered identical for all waste treatments and therefore activities beyond the “gate” of waste CFRP producing are not included. Maintenance and facility construction are also not included in the boundary. Process-specific data sources are supplemented by LCA databases (e.g., Eco-invent[4]) to develop full life cycle models. The functional unit of the study is 1 tonne waste CFRP from end life vehicle, which is assumed to have a CF content of 60wt% fibre contents [5]. The polymer matrix (40%wt) is assumed to be diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) epoxy resin. We examine energy use and green house emission representing environmental aspects, reported as CO₂ equivalent based on 100 year global warming potential (GWP) from IPCC 2013[6].

Outputs from waste treatment is out of the boundary of single life cycle regulated by traditional LCI referring ISO 14040 series[7]. When producing energy or recycled material from waste, we consider their reuse as raw energy or raw material into next life cycle. Thus, system expansion was applied in this study to qualify the benefit from substitution of raw energy or material. Recovered energy from incineration avoids electricity production from the UK grid and heat power production from natural gas. A range of scenarios are considered for composite materials produced from rCF and powder recyclates to displace conventional composite materials.

2.2 Life cycle cost

The goal for life cycle cost (LCC) analysis is to compare the financial impacts of the waste CFRP treatment routes and evaluate the trade-offs with environmental impacts. The system boundary of LCC is aligned with the LCI model and is applied to the total cost of all waste treatment including the activities of shredding, dismantling and waste treatment processes as well as transportation costs. Regulatory costs (e.g., “landfill tax”) are also considered. Waste treatment by landfilling and incineration are assessed based on recent UK tipping fee data for these conventional disposal routes [8]. A novel LCC model of mechanical recycling is developed here, taking into account treatment process costs as well as potential revenue from recyclates streams.

3 WASTE TREATMENT ROUTES ON CFRP

Both the LCI and LCC models begin where end-of-life vehicles have been collected. Activities upstream of this point (e.g. transport of vehicles) are common to all pathways considered here and therefore are not included in the models. Prior to undergoing waste treatments processes, CFRP waste components will undergo pre-treatment being shredded with other vehicle components (landfilling,

Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015

incineration) or being separated (dismantled) before shredding. The model of waste treatments includes landfilling, incineration and mechanical recycling shown in Figure 1. The shredding energy per unit waste in automotive scrap yard is 0.09 MJ/kg[9]. Dismantling process is assumed all based on manual work with no energy consumption. Transportation is required between the pre-treatment and treatment sites and the model is assumed 32 tonne standard dump truck being responsible for the logistic job. Eco-invent V3.0 database contributes most data sources without specific citation[4]. The whole model is demonstrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Model of waste treatments processes: landfilling, incineration and mechanical recycling

Major processes information includes: (1) CFRP waste pre-treatment cost including dismantling and shredding [12,13], (2) transportation to waste treatment site [10]; (3) waste treatment processes cost [8,12]; and (4) raw material price accounted for the benefit of recycled material [4,14]. All financial data has been converted to the 2014 UK pounds sterling. Unit delivering cost of collection, transfer to treatment sites and disposal is regarded as the same by using identical lorry, and estimated with the total value of time cost, mileage cost, job cost and profit based on the method in report [10]. The diesel price is given as the 2014 annual average of the UK which is 133 pence / litre[11].

3.1 Landfilling

The disposal of CFRP components in landfill is assumed to occur in a sanitary landfilling site which is normally a construction of a large pit with gravel, bituminous concrete and polyethylene sheet, thus the waste is insulated with the external environment to avoid groundwater contamination. Before transporting to landfill yard, car components needs to be shredded with the main vehicle body without prior dismantling and disposed of following metals separation into scarp and metal. All shredding work is done in a scrap yard located 100 km from landfill yard. Due to the largely inert nature of CFRP in landfill, no significant environmental impacts or associated costs are assumed to occur following disposal.

Costs associated with landfill are the sum of shredding cost, transport, and landfill tipping fees. Recent data on tipping fees in the UK reveal a cost of £21/tonne, excluding regulatory costs[8]. Landfill tax is applied to waste disposed of by landfill in the UK in order to encourage the use of more advanced waste treatment technologies that typically have higher tipping fees. Landfill tax results in an additional cost of landfilling CFRP waste of £80/tonne [15].

3.2 Incineration

Incineration of CFRP wastes enables the recovery of a portion of the embodied energy for useful purpose. Advanced incineration facilities can co-produce heat and electricity to supply local thermal

energy demands and to export electricity to the grid. Prior reports have suggested CFRP waste can be mixed with municipal waste and used as an energy source [5].

Before incineration, waste CFRP pre-treated similarly to the landfill route with shredding occurring at the scrap yard. Shredded CFRP waste is assumed to be transported 200 km to the incinerator.

The potential for energy production from CFRP waste is dependent on its energy content (carbon fibre and polymer matrix) and the efficiency of generating useful energy outputs (heat, electricity). Typical energy content of CFRP waste is approximately 30MJ/kg calorific value[12]. Based on the CFRP composition assumed here (60% fibre, 40% matrix), an energy content of 32 MJ/kg is calculated[16]. Waste incineration with energy recovery is typically less efficient than producing heat and electricity from fuels; electricity and heat generation efficiencies are assumed to be 13% and 25% respectively, giving a total conversion efficiency of 38%[4]. Electricity is assumed to displace the average UK generation mix comprised of 36% coal, 27% gas, 20% nuclear, 14.9% renewables and other sources [17]. Generated heat is assumed to displace heat production from natural gas combustion. Residue material following combustion (8% of CFRP waste) [4] is assumed to be disposed in landfill as described in section 3.1.

Emissions from incineration are modelled based on stoichiometric balances, assuming all carbon content of CFRP is oxidised and emitted as CO₂. Combustion of the carbon fibre component of CFRP waste emits 2.2 kg CO₂, while combustion of the polymer matrix releases 1.08 kg CO₂. Net greenhouse gas emissions are assessed by taking into account both the direct emissions from CFRP waste combustion and avoided emissions associated with displacing grid electricity and heat power from natural gas.

Financial analysis of waste CFRP incineration includes the cost of waste pre-treatment (shredding), transportation to the incineration site, and tipping fees based on recent UK data[8]. Revenue from selling electricity and heat products are assumed to be incorporated in the tipping fees charged to incoming waste and are therefore not included in this study.

3.3 Mechanical recycling

Mechanical recycling of CFRP waste involves size reduction processes and recovery of fibres and powder recyclates for reuse, which has been reported in several studies [14, 18, 19]; Waste CFRP is firstly cut into 50 to 100 mm size pieces by shredder and then grinded by hammer mill for further size reduction. Grading procedures using sieves and cyclones separate the recyclates into fibre- and power-rich fractions.

Greenhouse gas emission and energy use associated with mechanical recycling process are modelled including CFRP waste pre-treatment, energy consumption for size reduction processes, and the production of energy inputs (e.g. electricity generation). Waste CFRP from car components must be removed manually, thus an additional dismantling work has to be done before the composite material goes into recycling routes. CFRP components are initially shredded to 50 mm size before transport to the mechanical recycling facility. Transport distance is assumed to be 200 km in order to achieve sufficient scale of recycling operations, although this value is very hypothetical given that CFRP recycling facilities are mechanical recycling facilities do not exist in the UK. Energy requirements are dependent on final recyclates size and capacity; data here for 6mm hammer-mill screen size and 200t annual capacity[20]. The mass balances through the CFRP recycling process are shown in Figure 2. Mass balances for CFRP recyclates streams are estimated based on the assumed CFRP composition (60% fibre, 40% matrix) and data from the mechanical recycling of glass fibre composites [21] due to the lack of data specific to CFRP mechanical recycling.

Fibrous recyclates, termed here “recycled carbon fibres”(rCF) can be reused as reinforcement material in new composites by replacing a certain proportion of raw fibre material; however, there are limits of proportion of rCF that can be used without resulting in a significant degradation of material

Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015

properties[2]. Investigations into rCF used to replace virgin glass fibre (vGF) have shown mechanical properties are roughly similar with composites using 100% vGF[22]. Some literature claims rCF can be used to replace virgin carbon fibre(vCF) in direct injection moulding with nearly no degradation of mechanical properties[23]. However, numerous other reports evaluating vCF replacement with rCF have shown significant degradation of the mechanical properties of the resulting [24, 25]. Powder recyclates has the potential to replace raw filler material in polymer composites or aggregate materials[26].

LCC model of CFRP mechanical recycling is developed, including capital of facilities and operational costs, in addition to initial CFRP dismantling, shredding, and transportation. Capital costs are estimated based on Hedlund-Åström (2005) [18] and adjusted for the scale considered in the current study (200t/yr), equipment cost trends based on the CEPCI index [19], an assumed plant life of 10 years and an internal rate of return of 5%. Energy costs are quantified based on the UK industrial electricity price and fuel prices. Revenue from selling the CFRP recyclates – rCF and powder recyclates – are dependent on the uses for these materials and explained in more detail in the subsequent subsections. The net cost of CFRP mechanical recycling is determined as the balance of all costs (waste pre-treatment, transport, and recycling process) revenues.

Figure 2 Mechanical recycling

3.3.1 Glass fibre displacement

Following[27], fibrous CF recyclates (rCF) is assumed to displace glass fibres (GF) in composite materials at a ratio of 1 kg rCF: 1kg GF. After size reduction procedure of 1kg waste CFRP, the residue in two forms consists of 0.63 kg fibrous rCFRP and 0.35 kg powdered rCFRP, and 2% waste to landfill considering manufacture yield rate. 1.18 kg fibrous CFRP recyclate at 85% is needed to displace 1 kg vGF to maintain the same fibre content, so 1.87 kg waste CFRP must be recycled to generate enough fibre to displace 1kg GF.

Recycled rCF is assumed to be blended with virgin GF, unsaturated polyester resins and calcium carbonate filler to produce sheet moulding compound for subsequent component manufacture. A limited 20% rCF is considered and expected to maintain the same material properties as sheet moulding compound containing only virgin GF[27]. Production of composite components from rCF-blended sheet moulding compound is assumed to be identical to GF-based sheet moulding compound

in terms of energy consumption and cost. We estimate revenues from rCF sales by assuming rCF would receive the same price as virgin GF due to the 1:1 displacement ratio.

3.3.2 Filler displacement

Powdered recyclates arising from mechanical recycling of CFRPs have potential application as filler materials for a number of applications. In this study, we assume the powder fraction is a suitable substitute for calcium carbonate filler in the GF composite on a mass basis: 1kg powder recyclate will displace 1 kg calcium carbonate, thereby avoiding energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions associated with its production.

Besides, an extreme scenario is developed that all waste CFRP is grinded into powdered fraction. Net environmental and cost is based on the displacing ratio of 1 kg waste CFRP: 1kg filler. Revenue is regarded as selling filler.

3.3.3 Hypothetical carbon fibre replacement

Carbon fibre production is an energy intensive process which directly consumes about 183~286 MJ per kg, roughly 10 times as glass fibre production[20]; Greenhouse gas emissions associated with vCF production have been estimated previously 31 kg CO₂ eq[28]. Utilising CFRP recyclate to displace vCF in composite production is desirable for maximising revenue from waste streams and minimising energy use and greenhouse gas emissions; however, few large scale practices have been developed due to degradation composite mechanical properties incorporating CFRP recyclates. Following the approach of [23], we develop an LCI model for rCF displacing vCF considering degradation effects. A displacement factor γ_{CF} is introduced to represent 1 kg rCF required to displace γ_{CF} kg vCF.

4 RESULTS

Results of the eco-efficiency evaluation consist of both life cycle assessment and financial analysis on the three main routes of carbon fibre waste treatment: landfilling, incineration for energy recovery and mechanical recycling.

4.1 Eco-efficiency comparison of the waste treatment methods

Figure 3 presents both environmental and cost categories in a variety of routes: landfill with landfill tax or without tax, incineration by CHP incinerator, mechanical recycling for vGF replacement. The landfill tax scheme exerts a significant impact on financial consideration. Charging tax in landfilling shows the cost 12 % higher than the cost of incineration. When no charge landfill tax, the landfill route shows financial advantage over incineration where tax free landfill is 36% cheaper than the cost of incineration. In view of GWP, CFRP waste to incineration produced much more GHG emissions than landfilling. The power generation of electricity and heat from incineration can avoid emissions from general energy production; however, the credit of avoiding emission cannot compensate that much of waste burning, which still remains a significant amount.

Figure 3 also shows mechanical recycling to replace glass fibre is the best GHG emissions choice but the worst financial performance among incineration and landfill. From [4] ,1kg vGF production is associated with 1.9 kg CO₂ eq GHG emission. Avoiding emission (-1053.6 kg CO₂ eq) has much deficit over the emission associated with mechanical recycling (256.0 kg CO₂ eq). Dismantling as one of the major pre-processes emits nearly zero GHG emissions due to dominating manual work. However, GHG emissions benefit from recycling is at sake of high cost about 30 times of incineration and landfilling with tax.

In order to gauge the cost on reducing emissions, cost effective indicator is developed based on the cost difference over the amount of reduced emissions. Being the most emissions treatments with the least cost, incineration is selected as the reference flow on both net emissions and net cost. We

Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015

compare the cost effective issue on no tax landfilling and recycling based on the emission reduction from reference flow. From the data of Figure 3, only 0.008 £/ kg CO₂ eq for no tax landfilling is determined, while recycling treatment to replace glass fibre needs 1.6 £/ kg CO₂ eq. The replacement of virgin glass fibre by mechanical recycling shows a very positive environmental benefit but has the limitation of high cost due primarily to low profit of replaced vGF. To our knowledge, displacing glass fibre from rCF is currently the most realistic estimation via mechanical recycling. More usage scenarios are calculated in the following sensitivity analysis.

The proportion of each process cost is further examined. Dismantling work cost 1380£ and possesses 29% of total cost via mechanical recycling process. Results suggest design for easier dismantling of CFRP component has the potential to reduce the cost and possibly improve the manual pattern into more automated way. Transportation cost in each routes is less than 10£, which constituted small fraction among all scenarios while shredding work possessed major cost (70£) in both landfilling and incineration.

Figure 3 Comparison on landfilling with tax, landfilling without tax, incineration and mechanical recycling to replace glass fibre

4.2 Sensitivity analysis

The variance of recycled material use and energy efficiency plays an important role into final results. Filler displacement as another recycling candidate has been examined. Also, we construct a hypothetical scenario to displace vCF which may be the ideal routes of rCF, though this scenario is highly affected by degradation context. Besides, energy efficiency in CHP waste incinerator contributes another key factor on emissions.

4.2.1 Scenario 1: all recyclates displacing filler

To further explore the cost benefit in different usages of the recyclates, we examine the potential usage of extreme filler replacement. Displacing vGF is the reference scenario indicates fibrous like recyclates replaces the same fibre content of vGF and rest of powder-rich recyclates is used to displace filler. Scenario 1 assumes all the waste is shredded into powder recyclates as filler displacement. Figure 4 shows the GWP and cost comparison between reference scenario and scenario 1. In view of GWP, displacing vGF results in significant environmental benefits; displacing filler shows little credit due to minor emissions associated with filler production. Despite advantages of environmental impacts, scenario 1 consumes a large cost and shows little economic viability comparing with scenario 2. Displacing vGF or filler are both feasible treatments for potential industrial applications. Both results

suggest cheap or low end application such as filler is not worth to be displaced. Cost issue also determines displacing vGF from rCF is hard to apply in a large scale industry.

Figure 4 (a) GWP comparison on vGF displacement and filler displacement
(b) Cost comparison on vGF displacement and filler displacement

4.2.2 Scenario 2: displacing vCF considering degradation

Scenario 2 as a hypothetical scenario shows the fibrous like recyclates replace vCF and powder-rich recyclates displace filler as well.

Mechanical properties degradation of recycled product is a big hurdle of its using in real applications. The consequence of such degradation results in lower strength and modulus that restrains the rCF using for inferior application or more composite consumption. Due to no exact data on displacement ratio γ_{CF} , we investigate environmental and financial influences from a set of displacement ratio ranging from 0.1 to 1. The breakeven point for cost-benefit is at the displacing ratio of 0.93. Only if the displacing higher than that point, mechanical recycling method would make profit under current estimation. Note that aforementioned high dismantling cost makes the recycling process less-profitable. If only taking recycling cost into account, cost balance is at displacing ratio of 0.68. Instead, even at displacing ratio of 0.1, displacing rCF still shows credit on reducing GHG emissions where net emission is -1400 kg CO₂ eq due primarily to high energy consumption of vCF production. In order to achieve no tax landfilling cost effective value 0.008 £/ kg CO₂ eq, displacing ratio should be at 0.85.

4.2.3 Incinerator efficiency

Displacing energy amount is dependent on the efficiency of specific waste incinerators. The average energy conversion efficiency of CHP incinerator is primarily given to 12% for electricity generation and 24% for heat production. Efficiency improvement of waste incinerator has the potential to further reduce the emission intensity due to avoiding more raw energy product. Referring to the existing advanced CHP station using fossil fuel, high efficiency scenario of 25% in electricity conversion and 55% in heat conversion is assumed. To treat 1kg waste, low efficiency incinerator produces net 2.1kg CO₂ eq GHG gas and high efficiency produces 1.3kg CO₂ eq GHG gas.

5 DISCUSSION

Incineration is an acceptable recovery method regulating by end-of-life vehicles directive[16]. In the case of CFRP components, incineration becomes a more emission and cheaper choice than landfill due partially to the landfill tax charging. Results suggest regulations still have a potential to make a more elaborate adjustment based on the result of LCA and LCC. Careful using economic leverage is of importance to direct the waste into a more environmental friendly route.

Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015

Cost effective recycling method is the ultimate goal to treat composite waste though making recycled material from waste CFRP is a rather complex work. To evaluate the eco-efficiency impact of CFRP, more insightful work needs to be done concerning with detail production procedures with various form of recyclates. For example, this study makes assumption on the same density of recycled material and no interference with the business scale, which has an unknown impact. Thus, a more comprehensive model needs to be created to incorporate with the industrial feasibility.

Mechanical recycling is one of the simple methods to reclaim the recycled material. However, degradation issue becomes a big hurdle to use the recycled material into more advanced usage. Lower end usage such as filler replacement and glass fibre replacement has not shown much economic viable. Carbon fibre replacement scenario provides a possible benefit situation when the degradation is not that significant. Not pure fibre content and various shapes of fibrous recyclates from mechanical recycling play important roles into the degradation issue. More advanced technologies available to produce higher purity recycled carbon fibre should be taken into concern. According to the state of art of CFRP recycling, fluidised bed and pyrolysis methods are promising candidates. Much more purified fibre is recovered which can lead much higher displacement ratio between rCF and vCF. Ref [16] showed rCF from fluidised bed recycling was no significant degradation through the process. But much more capital investment is needed comparing the mechanical recycling method.

6 CONCLUSION

This work has studied the eco-efficiency of waste CFRP in three treatment routes: landfilling, incineration and recycling. Results vary significantly according to different route choices and different uses of recycled output. Some key factors may significantly impact the final decision; the final treatment decision may be largely impacted by some key factors found: landfill tax imposing, waste CHP incinerator efficiency, usage of recyclates and degradation grade.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project is supported by the Low Carbon Manufacturing of Automotive Products Innovation Team Project of Ningbo (2011B81006)

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Graedel, J. Allwood, J. Birat, B. Reck, S. Sibley, G. Sonnemann, *et al.*, "UNEP (2011) Recycling Rates of Metals-A Status Report," *A Report of the Working Group on the Global Metal Flows to the International Resource Panel, United Nations Environment Programme*, 2011.
- [2] S. Pickering, "Recycling technologies for thermoset composite materials—current status," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 37, pp. 1206-1215, 2006.
- [3] R. Heijungs and S. Suh, *The computational structure of life cycle assessment* vol. 11: Springer, 2002.
- [4] R. Hischier, "Ecoinvent data," *The life cycle inventory data version. Swiss Centre for Life Cycle Inventories, St. Gallen*, 2014.
- [5] R. A. Witik, R. Teuscher, V. Michaud, C. Ludwig, and J.-A. E. Månson, "Carbon fibre reinforced composite waste: an environmental assessment of recycling, energy

- recovery and landfilling," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 49, pp. 89-99, 2013.
- [6] T. Stocker, D. Qin, G. Plattner, M. Tignor, S. Allen, J. Boschung, *et al.*, "IPCC, 2013: climate change 2013: the physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change," 2013.
- [7] E. ISO, "14040: 2006," *Environmental management—Life cycle assessment—Principles and framework*, 2006.
- [8] Wrap, "Gate Fees Report 2013," 2013.
- [9] R. A. Witik, J. Payet, V. Michaud, C. Ludwig, and J.-A. E. Månson, "Assessing the life cycle costs and environmental performance of lightweight materials in automobile applications," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, pp. 1694-1709, 2011.
- [10] RHA, "RHA Cost Tables 2014," ed: RHA Weybridge, 2014.
- [11] DECC. (2014, Feb 12). *Road fuel and other petroleum product price statistics*. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/road-fuel-and-other-petroleum-product-prices>
- [12] A. Hedlund-Åström, "Model for end of life treatment of polymer composite materials," Doctoral thesis, Royal Institute of Technology, 2005.
- [13] Theshredderco. Available: <http://www.theshredderco.com/>
- [14] S. Pickering. (2005). *Routes to Recycling or Disposal of Thermoset Composites*. Available: <http://www.tech.plym.ac.uk/sme/mats324/Publications/LCA%20Workshop/Steve%20Pickering%20Nottingham.PPT>.
- [15] GOV.UK. (2014, Feb 12). *Environmental taxes, reliefs and schemes for businesses*. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/green-taxes-and-reliefs/overview>
- [16] S. J. Pickering, "Recycling Thermoset Composite Materials," *Wiley Encyclopedia of Composites*, 2012.
- [17] I. MacLeay, *Digest of United Kingdom energy statistics 2014*: The Stationery Office, 2014.
- [18] J. A. T. Palmer, E. Ken, and G. Oana, "Mechanical recycling of automotive composites for use as reinforcement in thermoset composites," 2009.
- [19] S. Pimenta and S. T. Pinho, "Recycling carbon fibre reinforced polymers for structural applications: Technology review and market outlook," *Waste management*, vol. 31, pp. 378-392, 2011.
- [20] J. Howarth, S. S. Mareddy, and P. T. Mativenga, "Energy intensity and environmental analysis of mechanical recycling of carbon fibre composite," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 81, pp. 46-50, 2014.

20th International Conference on Composite Materials

Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015

- [21] J. Scheirs, "Polymer recycling: science, technology and applications," *John! Wiley & Sons Ltd, Journals, Baffins Lane, Chichester, Sussex PO 19 1 UD, UK, 1998. 591, 1998.*
- [22] M. Janney and N. Baitcher, "Fabrication of chopped fiber preforms by the 3-DEP process. In: Composites and polycon. ," presented at the Tampa (FL, USA): American Composites Manufacturers Association, 2007.
- [23] J. Takahashi, N. Matsutsuka, T. Okazumi, K. Uzawa, I. Ohsawa, K. Yamaguchi, *et al.*, "Mechanical properties of recycled CFRP by injection molding method," *ICCM-16, Japan Society for Composite Materials, Kyoto, Japan, 2007.*
- [24] K. Ogi, T. Nishikawa, Y. Okano, and I. Taketa, "Mechanical properties of ABS resin reinforced with recycled CFRP," *Advanced Composite Materials*, vol. 16, pp. 181-194, 2007.
- [25] K. Larsen, "Recycling wind," *Reinforced plastics*, vol. 53, pp. 20-25, 2009.
- [26] A. Conroy, S. Halliwell, and T. Reynolds, "Composite recycling in the construction industry," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 37, pp. 1216-1222, 2006.
- [27] J. Palmer, L. Savage, O. Ghita, and K. Evans, "Sheet moulding compound (SMC) from carbon fibre recyclate," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 41, pp. 1232-1237, 2010.
- [28] S. Das, "Life cycle assessment of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites," *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 16, pp. 268-282, 2011.